

POSSIBILITIES OF TUTORING ACTIVITIES IN ORGANIZING FREE TIME OF STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITIES.

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is a noble girl. KokanDPI-teacher.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077171>

Abstract: Based on the goals of tutoring in family educational organizations, this article outlines considerations for the meaningful and effective organization of students' free time. The article presents tasks and recommendations within the content of the teacher's activities aimed at organizing students' free time.

Key words: tutor, purpose of tutoring, duties of a tutor, student's free time.

On December 25, 2020, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev visited the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan and during the meeting with young people, he expressed confidence that today's youth are a great force for the future of the nation. We count on your enthusiasm and determination. As you all know, we have set great goals for ourselves today. We began to create the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our Motherland. We consider the family, pre-school education, school and higher education, as well as scientific and cultural institutions to be the most important links in the future revival, therefore we are carrying out fundamental reforms in these areas. I believe that our dedicated and patriotic young people like you will actively participate in creating a new foundation for the development of our country and will make a worthy contribution," they said in their speech.

In recent years, the developing education system has undergone a number of innovations and changes, like any dynamically developing area of our country. The introduction and implementation of tutoring activities in oil educational institutions of our country has proven itself as a new type of activity in the life and development of youth. The activity content of tutoring includes the development and formation of student behavior, morality, discipline, desire to learn, and culture.

The purpose of tutoring activities is aimed at the development of students and youth and its purpose is to:

- effective organization of harmony of the educational and training process;
- regulation of the relationship between the educational institution and students;

- providing students with socio-spiritual and psychological support for a better understanding of themselves, studying and making the right decisions in life, increasing love for their chosen profession;
- increase the efficiency of the educational process in educational institutions, strengthen the public council and neighborhood in matters related to increasing student attendance;
- analyze students' learning of lessons and ensure that they spend their free time meaningfully; – constantly be aware of the social (marital) situation of the family.

Based on the purpose of this tutoring activity, the meaningful organization of students' free time is reflected in the content of the group teacher's activities. According to our people, the phrase "The free time of youth is the working time of the enemy" gives rise to the need for every possible increase in educational vigilance, increasing the consciousness and moral immunity of our youth.

A tutor is a person who promotes the personal development of students, worthy participation in university, republican and international competitions and olympiads, as well as the meaningful use of their free time, educates, engages in various scientific circles, studies their problems and shortcomings, and finds comprehensive solutions for them.

The group teacher carries out the following activities to organize students' free time.

Each mentor involves students in their assigned group in clubs and activities organized through five important initiatives, and creates opportunities for them to express their creativity and talents. Protects the rights and legitimate interests of students, helps create conditions for their education, study, living and recreation, informs them about the latest news.

Systematic work is also being carried out to strengthen the academic discipline of boys and girls, to develop such qualities as creative thinking, honesty, and correct speech. Talented and talented students will be identified and supported to participate in various competitions and olympiads, as well as to implement student projects and start-ups.

In addition, it monitors the level of students' learning of lessons, provides them with innovative educational technologies and educational materials, information resources, and creates the basis for the widespread and productive use of these resources.

At the same time, tutors solve a number of issues that concern students, in particular, the issue of creating a healthy environment among students through

the organization of systematic activities in student dormitories. To organize leisure time for students in student dormitories, the tutor carries out the following activities:

- organizing reading evenings;
- development of computer literacy;
- on the basis of attracting students to various meaningful circles, preparing them for public life;
- organization of sports competitions (chess, checkers, tennis, etc.) and clubs;
- ensure stability of students' mood and spirit through the organization of entertainment events;
- organization of creative evenings;

In a word, the mentor is one of the factors ensuring that students achieve the peaks of science, culture and spirituality, and becomes the students' closest assistant.

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